

Effect of Activity-Based Learning Method on Students' Achievement in Three-Dimensional Shapes in Senior Secondary Mathematics in Oruk Anam, Nigeria

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20187625>

Citation: Titu, E. C. (2026). Effect of Activity-Based Learning Method on Students' Achievement in Three-Dimensional Shapes in Senior Secondary Mathematics in Oruk Anam, Nigeria. *Global Journal of Modern Research and Emerging Trends*, 2(3). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20187625>

Abstract

This study investigated the effects of Activity-Based Learning (ABL) on the achievement of Senior Secondary One (SS1) students in three-dimensional shapes in mathematics in Oruk Anam Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. A quasi-experimental post-test-only non-equivalent control group design using intact classes was adopted. Two research questions and two hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and tested at the 0.05 level of significance. The target population comprised all 2,400 SS1 students in the 15 public secondary schools in Oruk Anam. A sample of 100 students from two randomly selected schools was initially enrolled; 79 students (experimental group: $n = 37$; control group: $n = 42$) completed the study and were included in the final analysis. The experimental group received instruction using ABL strategies, while the control group received

*conventional lecture instruction on the same 3D shapes content. The instrument used for data collection was the Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT), a 20-item four-option multiple-choice test on three-dimensional shapes. The instrument was validated by the researcher's supervisor using a table of specifications based on Bloom's taxonomy, and a reliability coefficient of $r = 0.99$ was obtained using the Spearman-Brown formula. Data were analysed using independent samples *t*-tests. Findings revealed a significant difference in the post-test achievement scores of students taught 3D shapes using ABL compared with those taught using the conventional lecture method. The findings also revealed no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught 3D shapes using ABL. It is recommended that ABL be adopted as the preferred instructional approach for geometry topics in Nigerian secondary schools.*

Keywords: Activity-based learning (abl), three-dimensional shapes, mathematics achievement, secondary school students, geometry instruction

1. Introduction

Education is a fundamental tool for intellectual growth and character development. The Federal Republic of Nigeria's National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013) affirms that education should foster critical and independent thinking, develop personal potential, and equip citizens to participate effectively in a democratic society. Mathematics occupies a pivotal role in this mission; it is made compulsory in both primary and secondary schools in Nigeria owing to its importance to individuals, the economy, and national development.

The scientific and technological development of any nation depends on the efforts made by that nation to advance its students' learning of mathematics and other mathematical sciences (Wonu & Arokoyu, 2016). The contributory role of mathematics to the curriculum cannot be overemphasised, especially in secondary schools. Despite the usefulness and benefits derived from the study of mathematics, there has been a persistent stereotype that mathematics is difficult. This stereotype has made a great number of people (especially learners) anxious and unable to live up to expectations, and this adversely affects their performance in external examinations such as the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) and the National Examinations Council (NECO) assessments.

Mathematics is also among the subjects most poorly taught and least understood in primary and secondary schools, a situation attributable to factors such as inadequate instructional approaches. The dominance of the conventional, teacher-centred, didactic method in Nigerian secondary schools limits student engagement and fails to foster deep conceptual understanding (Festus, 2013). Merely delivering a lesson as a lecture does not give learners an opportunity to participate actively.

Modern educational paradigms encourage student-centred approaches, where learners actively construct knowledge through exploration, experimentation, and real-world problem-solving (Centre for Education Innovations [CEI], 2021). In ABL, learners are expected to experiment and explore a given mathematical concept while the teacher supervises the activities. By practising the activities themselves, learners come to understand the procedures involved in the concept. A popular educational aphorism states, "What I hear I forget, what I see I remember, and what I do I understand," underscoring the need for teachers to use appropriate instructional materials in their lessons.

The outcome of the conventional teaching method, which is teacher-centred and didactic, has been consistently poor. This prompted the researcher to investigate the efficacy of the ABL method in teaching three-dimensional shapes to SS1 students, a level at which the foundational knowledge required for the senior certificate examination is established.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Many students find mathematics to be a difficult subject; anxiety engulfs them whenever they find themselves in a mathematics classroom, leading to poor performance in examinations. Research indicates that students understand and retain mathematical concepts more effectively when they are actively involved in the learning process (Oribhabor, 2020).

Also, research has shown that students understand and retain learning experiences with reference to the instructional strategy used. However, ABL is often neglected despite its essential role in facilitating the teaching and learning of mathematics in secondary schools. While studies such as Oribhabor (2020) and Celik (2018) have demonstrated the effectiveness of ABL in improving student achievement in mathematics generally, there is a notable gap in the literature specifically addressing the use of ABL for teaching three-dimensional shapes among SS1 students in Oruk Anam Local Government Area. Existing

studies have not examined whether the documented benefits of ABL transfer to this particular population and content area, nor have they accounted for the unique instructional challenges posed by the largely rural school contexts in Oruk Anam. This study, therefore, seeks to fill that gap by investigating the extent to which the ABL method improves students' achievement in three-dimensional shapes in Oruk Anam.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the effect of the ABL method on the teaching and learning of mathematics in Senior Secondary One (SS1). The specific objectives were as follows:

- i. To determine the effect of the ABL method on students' achievement in mathematics.
- ii. To examine the effect of the ABL method on students' achievement by gender.

1.3 Research Questions

The following research questions provided a guide to this study:

- i. What is the difference between the mean post-test achievement scores of students taught using ABL and those taught using the conventional lecture method?
- ii. What is the difference between the mean post-test achievement scores of male and female students taught using ABL?

1.4 Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

- i. H_{01} : There is no significant difference between the mean post-test achievement scores of students taught using ABL and those taught using the conventional lecture method.
- ii. H_{02} : There is no significant difference between the mean post-test achievement scores of male and female students taught using ABL.

1.5 Significance of the Study

This study examines the effect of the ABL method on Senior Secondary One (SS1) students' achievement in mathematics in Oruk Anam Local Government Area. It is noted that poor teaching approaches discourage students in the study of the subject. It is the expectation of the researcher that this study will provide teachers, educators, philosophers, psychologists, and prospective researchers with the necessary insight into the challenges

associated with the non-utilisation of appropriate teaching approaches. It is believed that the study may help mathematics teachers to review their techniques and approaches in order to meet the standards expected of them.

2. Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Framework

2.1.1 Activity-Based Learning (ABL)

Activity-based learning was first pioneered by David Horsburgh, a British-born educationist, in 1944. Activity-based learning is a methodology in which children learn at their own pace through various supervised activities. It is an engaging approach to learning, as it boosts brain development in children through constant stimulus and response.

The key feature of the ABL method is that it uses child-friendly educational aids to foster self-learning and allows a child to study according to his or her aptitude and skill. It is a child-centred, self-paced instructional methodology in which learners acquire knowledge through three core processes: experimentation (learning through direct experience), exploration (constructing knowledge through active investigation), and expression (communicating understanding through presentations and discussion) (CEI, 2021; Noreen et al., 2019).

In an ABL environment, the teacher is a facilitator, not a lecturer, directing learners through structured activities while providing formative feedback. Assessment is criterion-referenced rather than norm-referenced, as the goal is individual mastery rather than peer comparison. Instructional materials are central to ABL, enabling learners to manipulate, observe, and discover mathematical relationships independently.

Critics of ABL contend that it can be time-intensive and may sacrifice breadth of curriculum coverage (Noreen et al., 2019). Nevertheless, empirical studies consistently report that ABL yields higher achievement and greater engagement compared to traditional lecture methods.

2.1.2. Mathematics and the Secondary School Curriculum

Mathematics is defined by the Federal Republic of Nigeria's curriculum as a science of structure, order, and relation encompassing counting, measuring, logical reasoning, and

quantitative calculation (FRN, 2013). The definition covers virtually all aspects of human life, which makes mathematics an indispensable tool for the human race. In its study, mathematics has been developed into vast and diverse topics, which can be grouped into pure and applied mathematics.

In the Nigerian Senior Secondary School Curriculum (revised 2007), mathematics is organised into five themes: Number and Numeration, Algebraic Processes, Geometry, Statistics, and Introductory Calculus. The curriculum aims to develop positive attitudes towards mathematics, problem-solving competencies, mathematical language proficiency, and conceptual understanding appropriate to learners' developmental levels.

2.1.3 Geometry and Three-Dimensional Shapes

Geometry has its origin in the Greek meaning "earth measurement"; it is the visual study of shapes, sizes, and patterns and how they fit together in space. The Chambers Dictionary (1989 edition) defines geometry as a branch of mathematics that treats the properties of points, lines, surfaces, and solids. Research in mathematics education has established that 3D shapes present conceptual challenges for secondary school students, in part because they require learners to mentally coordinate spatial properties such as the relationship between a solid's face, edge, and vertex that cannot be fully appreciated through static diagrams alone (Wonu & Arokoyu, 2016). Van Hiele's (1986) model of geometric thinking suggests that most secondary school students operate at the visualisation and analysis levels, meaning they identify shapes by appearance rather than by property, and therefore benefit substantially from hands-on, activity-based instruction that makes the properties of 3D solids tangible.

Three-dimensional shapes like prisms, pyramids, cylinders, cones, and spheres are classified under the Mensuration theme of the Nigerian curriculum which require understanding of surface area, volume, and other cross-sectional properties. The practical relevance of geometry can be seen in architecture, engineering, navigation, and everyday construction, reinforcing the importance of effective pedagogical approaches to this content.

2.1.4 Gender, Mathematics Anxiety, and Instructional Method

The relationship between gender and mathematics achievement has been debated in literature. Historical research attributed performance gaps to biological differences, but contemporary scholarship attributes them predominantly to sociocultural factors, including mathematics anxiety and differential exposure to collaborative learning environments (Noreen et al., 2019). ABL, with its emphasis on group-based investigation and shared problem-solving, is theorised to reduce mathematics anxiety by distributing the cognitive and social burden of problem-solving across peers. This rationale justifies examining whether ABL differentially benefits male or female learners, particularly in a context such as Oruk Anam where gender norms may shape classroom participation.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 Cognitive Load Theory

The cognitive load theory, as developed by John Sweller in 1988, holds that for schema acquisition to occur, instruction should be designed to reduce working memory load (Sweller, 1988). The theory divides human cognitive processing into two components: long-term memory and working memory. Long-term memory has a large capacity and can store information for extended periods, while working memory has a limited capacity and combines temporary storage with the manipulation of information.

According to Sweller, the contents of long-term memory are sophisticated structures that permit us to perceive, think, and solve problems, rather than a collection of rote-learned facts. He further argued that since working memory has limited capacity, instructional methods should avoid overloading it.

In Sweller et al. (2011), the critical function of instruction, given the centrality of the information store, is to provide efficient and effective procedures for acquiring the information to be stored in long-term memory. This theory suggests that learning is most effective under conditions aligned with human cognitive architecture, meaning that teachers should adopt appropriate instructional methods and strategies to transmit the required knowledge and content to learners. Instructions should also be designed in a way that minimises working memory load and keeps extraneous cognitive load to a minimum during the learning process.

2.2.2 Thorndike's Laws of Learning

Edward Lee Thorndike (1874–1949) developed a connectionist theory of learning based on experimental work with animals (Okoro, 2002). He proposed three main laws of learning. The Law of Readiness holds that learning is most effective when the learner is prepared and motivated, emphasising that teachers must link new knowledge to prior experience. The Law of Exercise holds that stimulus-response bonds are strengthened through repeated practice, highlighting the value of continuous assessments and drills. The Law of Effect holds that behaviours followed by satisfying outcomes are more likely to recur; accordingly, teachers should provide prompt, positive reinforcement (Enang, 2006). ABL naturally operationalises these laws by creating motivating contexts for repeated practice and offering immediate corrective feedback.

2.3 Empirical Review

2.3.1 ABL and Student Achievement

Celik (2018) conducted a study with sixth-grade students in mathematics using an experimental research design, in which 78 students were divided into two groups by random assignment. The study, carried out over four weeks, revealed a noticeable performance advantage in the experimental group taught using the activity-based learning method.

Festus (2013) identified reasons for poor student performance in public examinations and highlighted several strategies to address this. He recommended the use of the ABL approach as a more effective alternative to conventional teaching.

Oribhabor (2020) conducted a study using a quasi-experimental pretest-posttest research design using intact classes. A sample of ninety-six (96) students from two secondary schools in Calabar Metropolis were given a 20-item essay mathematics test. It was indicated that students taught using the ABL method performed better than those taught using the lecture method. These findings collectively provide strong evidence for the efficacy of ABL in secondary mathematics education. These studies are directly relevant to the present study in that they demonstrate the consistent superiority of ABL over conventional lecture instruction across different school contexts and age groups. The present study extends this evidence base to SS1 students in Oruk Anam, a rural local

government area in Akwa Ibom State, thereby filling a geographic and contextual gap in the existing literature.

2.3.2 ABL and Gender Achievement in Mathematics

Mishra and Yadav (2013) carried out research on the effect of an activity-based learning approach on achievement in science at the elementary stage. A total of sixty (60) students participated of which thirty-five (35) were boys and twenty-five (25) were girls. and an experimental research design was used. The study concluded that gender had a significant influence on achievement in the experimental group, which was taught using the activity-based learning approach. Girls in the experimental group performed better than boys with respect to knowledge-based items. This study is relevant to the present investigation in that it raises the question of whether ABL produces differential gender outcomes, a question the present study examines specifically in the context of SS1 mathematics in Oruk Anam. The present study thus builds on and contextualises Mishra and Yadav's findings at the secondary school level.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The research design adopted for this study was a quasi-experimental post-test-only non-equivalent control group design. Intact classes were used because random assignment of individual students was not feasible. The SS1 classes served as the unit of assignment to the experimental and control conditions. The post-test-only design was appropriate because pre-test data were not collected. Group equivalence was addressed through the use of randomised school selection and intact class assignment.

3.2 Area of Study

This research study was carried out in Oruk Anam Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Oruk Anam lies between latitude 4°54'N and longitude 7°43'E, with a total population of approximately 172,000 people (FRN, 2006). Oruk Anam is regarded as the largest local government area in Akwa Ibom State by land area. The area hosts 15 co-educational public secondary schools.

3.3 Population and Sample

The study population comprised SS1 students in 15 co-educational public secondary schools in Oruk Anam Local Government Area, with a total population of approximately 2,400 students. Two schools were randomly selected from the 15, and 100 students from two intact SS1 classes were initially enrolled in the study (experimental group: $n = 50$; control group: $n = 50$). At the time of post-test administration, 21 students were absent and were excluded from the analysis, yielding a final analysable sample of 79 students (experimental group: $n = 37$; control group: $n = 42$). The experimental class received ABL instruction, while the control class received conventional lecture instruction on the same 3D shapes content.

3.4 Instrumentation

The instrument used in the data collection for this study was the Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) on the concept of 3D shapes, which consisted of two sections: Section A gathered demographic information (gender, class, and school name), and Section B contained 20 multiple-choice items structured on four options lettered A–D. Each correct response attracted one mark; incorrect or unanswered items attracted zero marks, giving a maximum score of 20.

3.5 Validity and Reliability

A modified Bloom's taxonomy of educational objectives was used to establish content validity, as shown in Table 1. The content selection covered three cognitive levels: knowledge, comprehension, and application. The instrument was reviewed by the supervisor, who made useful corrections and suggestions. The comments, corrections, and recommendations made by the supervisor were incorporated in constructing the final version of the instrument.

Table 1: Table of specification for the Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) on 3D shapes

Content	Knowledge	Comprehension	Application	Total
Identification and naming of 3D shapes	5	2	1	8
Basic properties of 3D shapes	3	1	1	5
Surface area and volume of shapes	2	0	5	7
Total	10	3	7	20

The instrument was administered once to twenty (20) SS1 students who were not part of the experiment. Thereafter, the reliability of the Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) was obtained using the split-half method. The test items were split into two comparable halves of odd and even items. The two sets of scores were correlated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and then corrected for full-test length using the Spearman-Brown formula. A reliability coefficient of $r = 0.99$ was obtained. This high value is attributable to the homogeneity of the test items, which were all drawn from a single, well-defined content domain (three-dimensional shapes at the SS1 level) and targeted only three cognitive levels (knowledge, comprehension, and application). The narrow cognitive and content scope reduces variability unrelated to the construct being measured, thereby producing a high inter-item consistency. The coefficient was therefore considered adequate for the study.

3.6 Treatment Procedure

Prior to commencing the study, written permission was obtained from the principals of both selected schools. Both groups were taught the same 3D shapes content from the SS1 mathematics curriculum over a period of 2 weeks, comprising 3 forty-minute lessons per week. The experimental group was taught using ABL strategies. In each lesson, the students were provided with physical 3D models (cardboard-constructed prisms, pyramids, cylinders, and cones) and guided through structured activities: identifying and naming each shape, counting faces, edges, and vertices, unfolding nets, and computing surface area and volume through measurement and calculation. The students worked in small groups, with

the teacher acting as facilitator, posing questions, correcting errors, and reinforcing correct procedures. Lesson plans were developed by the researcher prior to commencement.

The control group received the same content through conventional lecture instruction, with the teacher presenting definitions, properties, and worked examples on the chalkboard while students took notes and responded to teacher-directed questions. Following the treatment period, the MAT was administered to both groups as a post-test on the same day under standard conditions.

3.7 Method of Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics (means and standard deviations) were computed for both groups. Inferential analysis was conducted using independent samples two-tailed t-tests, tested at the 0.05 level of significance.

4. Results

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 2: Descriptive statistics for both groups on the post-test Mathematics Achievement Test.

Group	N	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Range	%
Experimental (ABL)	37	12.00	3.12	6	20	14	60.0%
Control (Lecture)	42	9.74	1.37	5	14	9	48.7%

The experimental group achieved a mean post-test score of 12.00 (SD = 3.12), equivalent to 60.0% of the maximum score, compared to 9.74 (SD = 1.37), or 48.7%, for the control group. Notably, both group means fall below the conventional 70% mastery threshold, which indicates that while ABL produced a meaningful advantage, achievement levels across both conditions suggest that further instructional support is warranted for full conceptual mastery of 3D shapes.

4.2 Hypothesis Testing

4.2.1 Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference between the mean post-test achievement scores of students taught using ABL and those taught using the conventional lecture method.

Table 3: Independent Samples t-Test: Post-Test Achievement Scores of the Experimental and Control Group

Groups	N	X	SD	df	t-cal	t-cri	Decision
Experimental group	37	12	3.1180				
				77	4.845	1.99	H01Rejected
Control Group	42	9.738	1.3711				

The results in Table 3 show that the mean post-test achievement score of students taught 3D shapes using the ABL method ($M = 12.00$) is greater than that of students taught using the lecture method ($M = 9.74$). The calculated t-value of 4.845 is greater than the critical t-value of 1.99 at 77 degrees of freedom and the 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected. The alternative hypothesis was subsequently upheld. Thus, there is a significant difference between the post-test achievement of students taught 3D shapes using the ABL method and those taught using the lecture method.

4.2.2 Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference between the mean post-test achievement scores of male and female students taught using ABL.

Table 4: Independent Samples t-Test: Post-Test Achievement by Gender (Experimental Group Only)

Gender	N	X	SD	df	t-cal	t-cri	Decision
Male	20	11.15	4.626				
				35	-1.7699	2.03	H02Accepted
Female	17	12.411	3.222				

Table 4 shows that the mean score of female students ($M = 12.41$, $SD = 3.22$) was slightly higher than that of males ($M = 11.15$, $SD = 4.63$). However, the calculated t-value is -1.7699 , while the critical value is 2.03 . Since the absolute value of the calculated t-value (1.7699) is less than the critical t-value (2.03), the null hypothesis is accepted. There is no statistically significant difference in post-test achievement between male and female students taught using ABL.

5. Discussion

5.1 Effect of ABL on Student Achievement

The findings from Table 3 indicate that students taught using the ABL method performed significantly better than their counterparts taught using the lecture method. This suggests that the ABL method was more effective in enhancing student achievement scores in mathematics than the lecture method.

These findings are consistent with Oribhabor (2020), who found that the activity-based learning method produced significantly higher achievement scores in students than the lecture method. The findings are also in line with those of Celik (2018), who observed a noticeable performance advantage in the group taught using the ABL method.

Theoretically, the result is explicable through Cognitive Load Theory (CLT), whereby ABL reduces extraneous cognitive load by anchoring abstract concepts such as surface area and volume in tangible, manipulative experiences, thereby freeing working memory resources for schema formation (Sweller et al., 2011). Thorndike's Law of Exercise further accounts for the advantage, as repeated hands-on practice strengthens stimulus-response bonds more robustly than passive reception of teacher-delivered content (Enang, 2006).

However, both the experimental ($M = 12.00$, 60%) and control groups ($M = 9.74$, 48.7%) fell below the conventional 70% mastery threshold, indicating that even with ABL, full conceptual mastery of 3D shapes was not achieved. This suggests that while ABL markedly outperforms lecture instruction, further curricular or pedagogical refinements, such as extended instructional time, peer tutoring, or additional formative assessment cycles, may be necessary to bring all students to mastery level.

5.2 Gender and Achievement under ABL

Findings from Table 4 showed that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female mathematics students taught the concept of 3D shapes using the ABL method. The result indicates that male and female students can perform comparably in learning mathematics when taught using a suitable method such as ABL.

The findings of this study are in disagreement with those of Mishra and Yadav (2013), whose results showed that female students taught using the ABL method at the elementary level performed better than their male counterparts. The difference may reflect the secondary-level context of the present study, where gender socialisation around mathematics is more entrenched, or the specific demands of 3D spatial reasoning, which some literature associates with greater male advantage.

5.3 Summary of the Findings

The findings of this study indicate that the ABL method has a significant effect on students' achievement in mathematics. The approach also produced higher achievement among students at the knowledge, comprehension, and application levels of the cognitive domain compared with the lecture method.

Also, when using the ABL method, there was no significant difference in academic achievement between male and female students. Thus, both male and female students can perform comparably when taught using the activity-based learning method in mathematics.

6. Conclusion And Recommendation

6.1 Conclusion

From the findings of this study, it was concluded that exposure of students to ABL may enhance academic achievement in three-dimensional shapes. It was also concluded that both male and female students appear to have benefited from the use of ABL to teach 3D shapes in this context. These findings suggest that ABL may serve as an effective and inclusive instructional strategy for secondary school mathematics in Oruk Anam and indicate that its broader adoption in schools where abstract geometry concepts remain a persistent source of student underachievement may be warranted. However, given that the study was limited to two schools in one local government area, these conclusions should be interpreted with caution and confirmed through further research before broader

generalisation. In all, the findings suggest that the ABL method may have a significant positive influence on senior secondary students' achievement in mathematics.

6.2 Implications of the Findings

The findings carry several implications for teachers, school administrators, and stakeholders in secondary mathematics education in Nigeria. For classroom teachers, the study demonstrates that a shift from didactic lecture to structured, hands-on ABL activities produces a large, meaningful improvement in student performance, particularly for a topic as spatially demanding as 3D shapes. For school administrators, the results justify investment in mathematics laboratories stocked with manipulative materials, including nets, 3D solid models, rulers, and measuring tools, as a cost-effective lever for raising achievement. For curriculum developers and examination bodies such as WAEC and NECO, the evidence supports formally integrating ABL-aligned activities into the recommended instructional approach for geometry topics in the national curriculum. For teacher training institutions, pre-service mathematics teacher education programmes should incorporate modules on designing and delivering ABL lessons, including effective use of manipulatives and formative feedback strategies.

6.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Every school should be provided with a mathematics laboratory to promote ABL and provide access to 3D instructional materials.
- ii. The teaching of mathematics (and other sciences) should be made more practical and less abstract through the use of the activity-based learning method.
- iii. The teaching of abstract mathematics concepts should be grounded in concrete, activity-based experiences to promote meaningful understanding beyond rote procedure.
- iv. Curriculum planning should include the use of the activity-based learning method in teaching other concepts in mathematics.

6.4 Suggestions for Further Study

The following suggestions for further study are hereby proposed:

- i. This study should be replicated using a pre-test/post-test design with random assignment to confirm group equivalence and strengthen causal inference.
- ii. The study should be extended to other abstract mathematics concepts (e.g., trigonometry, coordinate geometry) and to other geopolitical zones in Nigeria.
- iii. Longitudinal studies examining the sustained effect of ABL on mathematics achievement and attitude are recommended.
- iv. Future research should explore the specific design features of ABL (group size, material type, and feedback frequency) that most strongly predict achievement gains.

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